

Independent Processes and Higher Order Symmetries in Irreversible Thermodynamics

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Conditions under which higher order symmetries would be obeyed have been discussed in a manner more general than that done previously³. Certain new symmetry relations, which have hitherto gone unnoticed in literature, have been reported.

Li¹⁻² has shown that if the independent processes involved have ν th order independence, the ν th order coefficients would be symmetric. Recently, Rastogi, Srivastava and Singh³ have critically examined the phenomenological relations in chemical reactions and discussed the conditions under which the higher order symmetries would be obeyed. It has been shown³ by using the methods of chemical kinetics that in the case of monomolecular triangular isomerisation reactions, Onsager's reciprocal relations are obeyed but the higher order symmetries are not obeyed because the independent processes considered have only first order independence. But if the following reactions,

are taken to be the independent processes of the kinetic systems

the first order symmetries as well as the higher order symmetries are obeyed because the total process is a linear combination of the independent processes which have higher order independence. But this has been done only in a particular case of chemical reactions.

In this communication we aim at demonstrating in a general manner that whenever independent processes having ν th order independence are linearly combined in the following two ways,

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 2J'_1 = J_1 + J_2 \\ 2J'_2 = J_1 - J_2 \\ X'_1 = X_1 + X_2 \\ X'_2 = X_1 - X_2 \end{array} \right\} \dots\dots (1)$$

and

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} J'_1 = J_1 + nJ_2 \\ J'_2 = J_2 \\ X'_1 = X_1 \\ X'_2 = X_2 - nX_1 \end{array} \right\} \dots\dots (2)$$

where J_1, J_2 are the fluxes and X_1, X_2 are the corresponding forces of the independent processes and J'_1, J'_2 are the fluxes and X'_1, X'_2 are the corresponding forces of the total

1. J. C. M. Li, *J. Chem. Physics*, 1958, **29**, 747.
2. J. C. M. Li, *J. Appl. Physics*, 1962, **33**, 616.
3. R. P. Rastogi, R. C. Srivastava and K. Singh, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1965, **61**, 854.

process, n being any positive real number, to describe the total process, the ν th order symmetries will always be satisfied provided the new choice of conjugate fluxes and forces does not alter the value of entropy production written as the sum of the products of fluxes and forces.

Linearly Combined Independent Processes: Let us first consider the case when J'_1 and J'_2 , the new fluxes and X'_1 and X'_2 , the new corresponding forces of the total process and the fluxes J_1, J_2 and the corresponding forces X_1, X_2 of the independent processes are linearly related in the manner given by equation (1). Phenomenological relations for the independent processes can be written as

$$J_1 = f(X_1) \dots\dots (3)$$

$$J_2 = f(X_2) \dots\dots (4)$$

By making use of Taylor's expansion around equilibrium the equations(3) and (4) can be rewritten in the form

$$J_1 = \left(\frac{\partial J_1}{\partial X_1}\right)_0 X_1 + \frac{1}{2!} \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2}\right)_0 X_1^2 + \dots (5)$$

$$J_2 = \left(\frac{\partial J_2}{\partial X_2}\right)_0 X_2 + \frac{1}{2!} \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_2}{\partial X_2^2}\right)_0 X_2^2 + \dots (6)$$

where $\left(\frac{\partial J_1}{\partial X_1}\right)_0, \left(\frac{\partial J_2}{\partial X_2}\right)_0, \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2}\right)_0, \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_2}{\partial X_2^2}\right)_0$ etc. refer to the equilibrium situation.

It can be seen that the relationship⁴

$$\sigma = J_1 X_1 + J_2 X_2 = J'_1 X'_1 + J'_2 X'_2 \dots\dots (7)$$

σ being the entropy production, is not violated by the new choice of fluxes and forces.

From equations (1), (5) and (6) we can write

$$\begin{aligned} 2 J'_1 = & \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{\partial J_1}{\partial X_1}\right)_0 + \left(\frac{\partial J_2}{\partial X_2}\right)_0 \right] X'_1 + \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{\partial J_1}{\partial X_1}\right)_0 - \left(\frac{\partial J_2}{\partial X_2}\right)_0 \right] X'_2 \\ & + \frac{1}{4} \frac{1}{2!} \left[\left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2}\right)_0 + \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_2}{\partial X_2^2}\right)_0 \right] X'^2_1 + \frac{1}{4} \frac{1}{2!} \left[\left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2}\right)_0 - \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_2}{\partial X_2^2}\right)_0 \right] X'^2_2 \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{2!} \left[\left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2}\right)_0 - \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_2}{\partial X_2^2}\right)_0 \right] X'_1 \cdot X'_2 + \dots\dots (8) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} 2 J'_2 = & \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{\partial J_1}{\partial X_1}\right)_0 - \left(\frac{\partial J_2}{\partial X_2}\right)_0 \right] X'_1 + \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{\partial J_1}{\partial X_1}\right)_0 + \left(\frac{\partial J_2}{\partial X_2}\right)_0 \right] X'_2 \\ & + \frac{1}{4} \frac{1}{2!} \left[\left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2}\right)_0 - \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_2}{\partial X_2^2}\right)_0 \right] X'^2_1 + \frac{1}{4} \frac{1}{2!} \left[\left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2}\right)_0 - \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_2}{\partial X_2^2}\right)_0 \right] X'^2_2 \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{2!} \left[\left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2}\right)_0 + \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_2}{\partial X_2^2}\right)_0 \right] X'_1 \cdot X'_2 + \dots\dots (9) \end{aligned}$$

4. S. R. de Groot and P. Mazur, "Non-equilibrium Thermodynamics," North Holland Publishing Co., Amsterdam, 1962.

Equations (8) and (9) are the phenomenological relations of the form^{1,2}

$$J'_1 = L_{11} X'_1 + L_{12} X'_2 + L_{111} X'^2_1 + L_{122} X'^2_2 + L_{112} X'_1 X'_2 + \dots \quad \text{---(10)}$$

$$J'_2 = L_{21} X'_1 + L_{22} X'_2 + L_{211} X'^2_1 + L_{222} X'^2_2 + L_{212} X'_1 X'_2 + \dots \quad \text{---(11)}$$

where L s represent the phenomenological coefficients. From equations (8), (9), (10) and (11) it can be seen that

$$L_{12} = L_{21} ; L_{112} = 2 L_{211} ; L_{212} = 2 L_{122} \quad \dots \dots \text{(12)}$$

$$L_{111} = L_{222} ; L_{1111} = L_{1222} ; L_{2222} = L_{2111} \quad \dots \dots \text{(13)}$$

The relationships given by equations (13) are new symmetry relations and have so far gone/unnoticed in literature^{1,2,3}.

Another Case: In this section we proceed to consider the next case where J_1, J_2, X_1, X_2 are related to J'_1, J'_2, X'_1, X'_2 , in the manner given by equation (2).

Following the procedure adopted in the preceding section of this paper we can write

$$J'_1 = \left[\left(\frac{\partial J_1}{\partial X_1} \right)_0 + n^2 \left(\frac{\partial J_2}{\partial X_2} \right)_0 \right] X'_1 + n \left(\frac{\partial J_2}{\partial X_2} \right)_0 X'_2 + \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2} \right)_0 + n^3 \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_2}{\partial X_2^2} \right)_0 \right] X'^2_1 + \frac{1}{2} n \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_2}{\partial X_2^2} \right)_0 X'^2_2 + n^2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_2}{\partial X_2^2} \right)_0 X'_1 X'_2 + \dots \quad \text{---(14)}$$

$$J'_2 = n \left(\frac{\partial J_2}{\partial X_2} \right)_0 X'_1 + \left(\frac{\partial J_2}{\partial X_2} \right)_0 X'_2 + \frac{1}{2} n^2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_2}{\partial X_2^2} \right)_0 X'^2_1 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_2}{\partial X_2^2} \right)_0 X'^2_2 + n \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_2}{\partial X_2^2} \right)_0 X'_1 X'_2 + \dots \quad \text{---(15)}$$

Equations (14) and (15) have the same form as the equations (10) and (11). A perusal of equations (14) and (15) again reveals that the symmetry relations given by equation (12) are satisfied in this case also. However, the new symmetry relations given by equation (13) are not satisfied in this case.

Thus we have shown that the higher order symmetries given by equation (12) are valid under the condition more general than that considered previously³. However, it must be admitted that since in this paper we have considered only a restricted class of

linear transformations, given by equations (1) and (2), it is difficult to claim that higher order symmetry relations are satisfied for any group of linear transformation of fluxes and forces as is the case with the Onsager's reciprocal relations.

The authors are grateful to Professor R. P. Rastogi, Head of the Chemistry Department, University of Gorakhpur, for drawing our attention to this problem and advice.

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Received, January 20, 1966.